

ISic1144

I.Sicily inscription 1144

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, private house

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140629

1. Μά[ξ]ιμος

2. Ἰάσονος

3. ἐτῶν ζ.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492757

EDCS 39102301

PHI 140629

Bibliography

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